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COVER ART – The cover art was painted by Jason Poole and depicts a school of Mosasaurs.

CETACEAN REMAINS FROM THE LOWER OLIGOCENE OLD CHURCH FORMATION OF VIRGINIA

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ABSTRACT -- Remains of six types of Oligocene cetaceans have been recovered from the outcrop region of the Old Church Formation in the Atlantic Coastal Plain of east-central Virginia. These remains provide the first glimpse of the cetacean fauna that lived north of modern Cape Hatteras during the Oligocene. Two kinds of mysticetes are represented (aff. *Coronodon* sp. and *Micromysticetus* sp.), and four kinds of odontocetes (cf. *Ankylorhiza* sp., cf. *Xenorophus sloanii*, Xenorophidae aff. *Cotylocara* and *Echovenator*, and aff. *Eosqualodon* sp.). In detail, the mysticete portion of this fauna is different and somewhat less advanced than the mysticete fauna found in the Givhans Ferry Member of the Ashley Formation, indicating that the Old Church Formation probably is correlative with either the middle or lower member of the Rupelian Ashley Formation in South Carolina. The odontocete portion of this fauna is also compatible with the middle or lower members of the Ashley Formation, except for *Eosqualodon* sp. which probably came from a Chattian-age “phantom unit” that is correlative with the Chandler Bridge Formation of South Carolina but now eroded away

INTRODUCTION

Prior to 1960, only sparse Oligocene whale remains were known from anywhere in the eastern United States. These included only three described species: *Agorophius pygmaeus* (Müller, 1849), *Archaeodelphis patrius* (Allen, 1921), and *Xenorophus sloanii* (Kellogg, 1923a), and all of them came from the vicinity of Charleston, South Carolina. Starting in the 1960's, urban expansion into the region northwest of Charleston opened up numerous new outcrops of Oligocene strata in two formations, the lower

Oligocene (Rupelian) Ashley Formation (Weems and Lemon, 1984; Weems and Lewis, 2002) and the upper Oligocene (Chattian) Chandler Bridge Formation (Sanders and others, 1982; Weems and Lewis, 2002). During this time, local collectors affiliated with the Charleston Museum, South Carolina State Museum, and the Mace Brown Museum of Natural History discovered, collected, and donated a large volume of new and mostly undescribed Oligocene vertebrate material. Among this material are numerous new cetacean taxa, and many of these have been described in recent years (Sanders and Barnes, 2002a, 2002b;

Geisler and others, 2014; Sanders and Geisler, 2015; Churchill and others, 2016; Godfrey and others, 2016; Boessenecker and others, 2017a, 2017b; Geisler and others, 2017; Boessenecker and Geisler, 2018; Boessenecker and others, 2020).

Although numerous outcrops of richly fossiliferous Oligocene strata have been intensely collected in South Carolina over the past fifty years, outcrops of Oligocene strata in North Carolina and Virginia are rare and little visited (Figure 1). As a result, only two recent papers have been published on material from North Carolina. One is by Uhen (2008), who described a new species of Oligocene xenorophid dolphin (*Albertocetus meffordorum*) that probably came from the Belgrade Formation of North Carolina, and the other is by Boessenecker and others (2017b) who described earbones of a different xenorophid (*Echovenator* sp.) from quarry exposures of the Belgrade Formation near Maysville, North Carolina. No unequivocal Oligocene whale material has been reported so far from Virginia, though there is one published anecdote. Ward (1984, p. 53), in describing the content of the basal lag bed of the middle Miocene Plum Point Member of the Calvert Formation at Gravatts Mill in King William County, Virginia (37.7686 N, 77.2826 W), alluded to an unfigured “periotic from an odontocete whale that was certainly pre-Calvert and probably early

Miocene or very late Oligocene in age.” No other reference to this specimen is known to the present authors.

In great measure, the lack of any literature concerning Old Church Formation cetaceans stems from the fact that outcrops of this unit are extremely sparse, being mostly concentrated in a few areas along the banks of the Pamunkey River and in a few borrow pits (now flooded) about ten miles to the south in the Chickahominy River Valley (Ward, 1984, p. 52). Although the Old Church Formation has yielded a rich molluscan and microvertebrate fauna (Ward, 1984; Müller, 1999), macrovertebrate remains are encountered only rarely. These include sparse sea turtle remains of *Ashleychelys palmeri*, *Carolinochelys wilsoni*, and *Procolpochelys charlestonensis* (Weems, 2014), a densely ossified sirenian rib fragment, and the whale remains reported here. These cetacean remains were collected in recent years by a number of dedicated amateurs, who have recovered a small but significant sample of whale specimens from the Pamunkey River outcrops within the outcrop belt of the Old Church Formation. These remains can be identified well enough to establish the former presence of two kinds of mysticete and four kinds of odontocete whales. These are discussed and illustrated as follows:

Figure 1

Figure 1. Regional map of the southeastern Atlantic Coastal Plain showing localities (stars) where Oligocene whale remains have been found. 1, Charleston region, South Carolina; 2, Onslow Beach area, North Carolina; 3, Pamunkey River Valley, Virginia. The circle labeled "L" marks the location of the USGS-NASA Langley corehole.

Figure 2. Correlation chart of outcropping whale-bearing Oligocene strata in Virginia and South Carolina. South Carolina stratigraphy from Weems and others (2016). The Old Church Formation probably only correlates with the middle or lower member of the Ashley Formation, but at present there is no way to determine which one.

INSTITUTIONAL ABBREVIATIONS

CMM-V, Calvert Marine Museum, Vertebrate Paleontology collection; ChM PV, Charleston Museum, Vertebrate Paleontology collection; CCNHM, College of Charleston, Natural History Museum collection.

SYSTEMATIC PALEONTOLOGY

MAMMALIA Linnaeus, 1758

CETACEA Brisson, 1762

MYSTICETI Flower, 1864

Family undefined

aff. *Coronodon* sp.

Figure 3A

Material – CMM-V-4354, one cheek tooth with complete crown but lacking one root; CMM-V-4349, one heavily worn cheek tooth.

Collectors – CMM-V-4354, Mark Bennett; CMM-V-4349, Ron Ison.

Horizon and Age – Old Church Formation, Rupelian, early Oligocene.

Discussion – These two specimens are reminiscent of *Coronodon havensteini* (Geisler and others, 2017), a large toothed-mysticete recently described from the Runnymede Marl Member of the Ashley Formation in South Carolina (Figure 2). The Old Church toothed-mysticete cheek teeth are distinctly smaller than *Coronodon havensteini*, but share radially oriented accessory cusps, mostly smooth enamel, a lack of lingual or labial cingulae, a main cusp that is not drastically larger than the adjacent accessory cusps, and a double-root with a long isthmus below the crown. Although these teeth are probably referable to *Coronodon*, they pertain to an undescribed species smaller than the type species *Coronodon havensteini*. Geisler and others (2017) interpreted *Coronodon* as both an

active macrophagous predator and a bulk filter-feeder, thus being an evolutionary link between the macrophagous predator ancestors of mysticetes and the bulk filter-feeders they later became.

A potential caveat is that teeth of this type apparently also evolved in at least one strange lineage of Miocene odontocetes represented by *Inticetus vertizi* (Lambert et al., 2018) from the lower Miocene of Peru and cf. *Phococetus* sp. (Boessenecker, 2019) from the lower Miocene of the North Atlantic. Owing to the incredible dental diversity of Oligocene cetaceans, a possible odontocete affinity for this tooth cannot be ruled out at present.

EOMYSTICETIDAE Sanders and Barnes, 2002a

Micromysticetus Sanders and Barnes, 2002b

Micromysticetus sp.

Figure 3B

Material – CMM-V-5011, periotic; CMM-V-5010.

Collector – Robert E. Weems.

Horizon and Age – Found on beach at base of bluff that exposes only the Old Church Formation, Rupelian, early Oligocene.

Discussion – This periotic is very similar to the periotic of *Micromysticetus rothauseni* except that it is distinctly smaller. CMM-V-5011 shares with *Micromysticetus rothauseni*, to the exclusion of other eomysticetids, the following combination of features: a longitudinal ventral ridge on the pars cochlearis, a posterior bullar facet with two faces (shared with *Eomysticetus*), a rectangular anterior process (also shared with *Eomysticetus*), and a relatively transversely narrow and distally pointed posterior process (shared with *Matapanui*, *Tohoraata*, *Tokarahia*, and *Waharoa*). The Eomysticetidae were adapted to bulk filter-feeding and thus lie close to the line leading to modern mysticete whales.

Figure 3. Cetaceans from the Old Church Formation. A. CMM-V-4354, cheek tooth of the toothed-mysticete, aff. *Coronodon* sp. B. Three views of periotic (CMM-V-5011) of *Micromysticetus* sp. C. CMM-V-4347, cheek tooth of cf. *Ankylorhiza* sp. D. CMM-V-4846, cheek tooth of cf. *Xenorophus sloanii*. E. CMM-V-4847, cheek tooth of aff *Eosqualodon* sp.

? *Micromysticetus* sp.

Figure 4

Material – CMM-V-5009, one nearly complete posterior lumbar vertebra.

Collector – Aaron A. Alford

Horizon and Age – Old Church Formation, Rupelian, early Oligocene.

Discussion – This specimen was found in situ within the Old Church Formation, so its stratigraphic provenance is not in question. The base of the centrum bears slight protuberances on its posterior border, indicating that this vertebra was from near the posterior end of the lumbar series. The epiphyses are fused to the centrum, so the animal was an adult when it died. It is about 85% of the size of the larger posterior lumbar among the type material of *E. whitmorei*.

As is true today, the largest whales in the Ashley and Chandler Bridge faunas were mysticetes. Four mysticete species are known to have reached a size comparable to that of the vertebra illustrated here. One was *Micromysticetus rothouseni*, which came from the Ashley Formation (Sanders and Barnes, 2002b). Its type specimen was a juvenile, and more recent work based on adult skull material shows that this species was much larger than previously thought and larger than the type specimen of *Eomysticetus whitmorei* (Boessenecker and

Fordyce, 2017), which suggests that its lumbar vertebrae were likely in the size range of the lumbar vertebrae of *Eomysticetus*. Two other large Oligocene mysticete species belonged to the genus *Eomysticetus*: *E. whitmorei* and *E. carolinensis* (Sanders and Barnes, 2002a). The fourth large taxon is a large, undescribed toothed mysticete closely related to *Coronodon*. *Micromysticetus* comes from the early Oligocene Ashley Formation, while the other three taxa are only known from the late Oligocene Chandler Bridge Formation.

The lumbar vertebrae of *Micromysticetus* are unknown, but lumbar vertebrae are known for the other three taxa. *Eomysticetus* has strongly downturned transverse processes on its lumbar vertebrae and in this trait is quite similar to the Old Church Formation lumbar vertebra described here. In contrast, the lumbar vertebra of the *Coronodon*-like mysticete does not have strongly downturned transverse processes (Fig. 5) nor does it have vertebrae with centrum proportions similar to the centrum proportions found both in the vertebra described here and in the posterior lumbar-anterior caudal vertebrae of *Eomysticetus*. For all of these reasons, the lumbar vertebra illustrated here can be confidently assigned to the Eomysticetidae rather than to a *Coronodon*-like mysticete. As *Eomysticetus* is unknown from strata as old as the Ashley Formation, association of this vertebra with *Micromysticetus* is likely.

Figure 4. Posterior lumbar (CMM-V-5009) of *Micromysticetus* sp. A posterior view; B, anterior view; C, dorsal view; D, ventral view; E, left lateral view.

large Ashley archaeomysticete
(anterior caudal)

Aetiocetus cotylalveus
(first caudal)

Eomysticetus whitmorei
(anterior caudal)

Figure 5. Left side, anterior caudal vertebra of a large, unnamed Chandler Bridge Formation *Coronodon*-like toothed-mysticete whale (ChM PV 5720). Right side top, anterior view of anterior caudal vertebra of the archaic filter-feeding Oligocene mysticete whale *Aetiocetus cotylalveus* (adapted from Emlong, 1966). Bottom right, anterior view of anterior caudal vertebra of *Eomysticetus whitmorei*.

ODONTOCETI Flower, 1867**Family indet.****cf. *Ankylorhiza* sp.**

Figures 3C, 7A-D, 7I-K

Material – CMM-V-4347, cheek tooth; CMM-V-9628, bulla; CMM-V-9630, periotic.

Collectors – CMM-V-4347 collected by Kurt Butler; CMM-V-9628 and CMM-V-9630 collected by Aaron Alford.

Horizon and Age – Old Church Formation, Rupelian, early Oligocene.

Discussion – The cheek tooth was found on the beach at the base of the same bluff that yielded the periotic of *Micromysticetus* (CMM-V-5011). This tooth resembles *Squalodon* in its large size, double-rooted condition, thickened cementum, and large triangular crown with distinct cutting edges, but it does not pertain to either species of *Squalodon* known from the Calvert Formation (Dooley, 2005; Kellogg, 1923b) because the distal root tips in this specimen strongly diverge from each other and accessory cusps are lacking. In *Squalodon*, the root tips are parallel to each other or are nearly convergent. This tooth may belong to the large macrophagous odontocete *Ankylorhiza* (Boessenecker and others, 2020). At least two species referable to this genus are preserved in the Oligocene strata of South Carolina, including *Ankylorhiza tiedemani* (Ashley and Chandler Bridge formations) and a second, larger unnamed species from the Chandler Bridge Formation. The periotic and bulla described here were found on the river bottom beneath the bluff where the cheek tooth was found; they also probably pertain to *Ankylorhiza*.

Xenorophidae**cf. *Xenorophus sloanii***

Figures 6A-E

Material – CMM-V-4846, cheek tooth.

Collector – Ron Ison

Horizon and Age – Old Church Formation, Rupelian, early Oligocene.

Discussion – This tooth was found along the Pamunkey River bottom in the vicinity of outcrops of the Old Church Formation. The strong separation of the roots of this tooth indicate that it cannot pertain to either of the Calvert Formation species of *Squalodon* (Kellogg, 1923b; Dooley, 2003, 2005), which are the only other teeth known from this area that have even a remotely similar root morphology. At the same time, the presence of well-developed but small denticles on the crown of this molariform tooth also make it different from other known squalodontid cheek teeth. Teeth of this morphology are generally characteristic of some xenorophids and also agorophiid-grade and waipatiid-grade odontocetes. However, the triangular, straight carinae with small denticles and the presence of weak lingual and labial cingulae strongly suggest identification as a lower molar of a xenorophid dolphin. Among xenorophid dolphins, the large size and presence of apicobasally elongated nodular enamel texture on this tooth is most similar to the teeth of the large xenorophid *Xenorophus sloanii*.

aff. *Cotylocara* sp. and *Echovenator* sp.

Figures 6F-J

Material – CMM-V-9260, cheek tooth.

Collector – Aaron Alford

Horizon and Age – Old Church Formation, Rupelian, early Oligocene.

Discussion – This tooth was collected directly from the matrix of the Old Church Formation. It is also a xenorophid tooth, but not from the same taxon as the one above referred to cf. *Xenorophus sloanii*. It is very similar to the cheek teeth of

Cotylocara and *Echovenator*, both of which come from the Chandler Bridge Formation. Because this Old Church specimen comes from a

somewhat older horizon, it may well pertain to an ancestral species of one or both of these taxa.

Figure 6. A-E, Views of a tooth of *cf. Xenorophus sloanii* in internal, anterior, external, posterior, and occlusal views. F-J, Views of a xenorophid tooth (aff. *Cotylocara* and *Echovenator*) in internal, anterior, external, posterior, and occlusal views.

Family indet.

aff. *Eosqualodon* sp.

Figure 3E

Material – CMM-V-4847, cheek tooth.

Collector – Ron Ison

Horizon and Age – Erosionally removed “phantom unit”, Chattian, late Oligocene.

Discussion – This tooth is much larger than the tooth referred to cf. *Xenorophus sloanii* and is triangular with large accessory cusps, rugose enamel, a crown lacking any cingula, and a double root with a long isthmus. Teeth of two

odontocetes from the Oligocene of South Carolina are similar to this: an unidentified agorophiid-grade dolphin represented by ChM PV 2761 that is possibly closely related to *Ankylorhiza* (Boessenecker and others, 2020: figure 3), and specimens preliminarily referred to *Eosqualodon* from the Chandler Bridge Formation, a genus previously known only from the upper Oligocene (Chattian) of Germany (Rothausen, 1968) and the basal Miocene (Aquitanian) of Italy (Capellini, 1903). CMM-V-4847 bears more strongly ornamented enamel than teeth of *Eosqualodon* sp. from the Chandler Bridge Formation (CCNHM 170), and it is smaller than the preserved teeth of the agorophiid-grade dolphin ChM PV 2761.

Figure 7. A-D, periotic of *Ankylorhiza* sp. E-H, xenorophid tympanic bulla, I-K, tympanic bulla of *Ankylorhiza* sp.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

Oligocene cetacean remains are rare in Virginia, but even so six distinctly different morphotypes can be recognized. Mysticete remains include a cetacean with *Coronodon*-like teeth and *Micromysticetus*. These mysticetes are similar to, but not identical with, mysticetes known from the upper Ashley and Chandler Bridge formations farther south in South Carolina. Although the mysticetes in the Old Church Formation are the same at a generic level with those in the Givhans Ferry Member of the Ashley and the Chandler Bridge formations, in both cases the Old Church specimens represent species that are somewhat smaller than the species of these genera found in the Givhans Ferry Member of the Ashley Formation and in the Chandler Bridge Formation. This suggests, but does not yet prove, that these Old Church Formation species are slightly older than the related species found in the Givhans Ferry Member of the Ashley Formation. The eomysticetid vertebra here associated with *Micromysticetus* came directly from the Old Church Formation. In South Carolina, *Micromysticetus* is only found in the Ashley Formation and not in the Chandler Bridge Formation (Sanders and Barnes, 2002a). Similarly, the better preserved *Coronodon*-like tooth (Fig. 3A) is nearly pristine in appearance except for its one broken off root lobe and, like *Micromysticetus*, it is similar to a species known from the Ashley Formation and unlike the species known from the Chandler Bridge Formation. All of these factors support the conclusion that these specimens came from the Old Church Formation (equivalent in age to the Ashley Formation) and not from any other stratigraphic interval.

Oligocene odontocete teeth from the stretch of the Pamunkey River where the Old Church Formation crops out closely resemble five taxa from the Oligocene Ashley and Chandler Bridge formations of South Carolina: *Xenorophus*, *Cotylocara*, *Echovenator*, *Ankylorhiza*, and *Eosqualodon*. *Xenorophus* and *Ankylorhiza* are

two of the more commonly recovered odontocete genera in the Charleston embayment, and they are known from both the Ashley and Chandler Bridge formations. The genera *Cotylocara* and *Echovenator* are so far only known from the Chandler Bridge Formation, but they are relatively rare taxa and it is entirely possible that they were represented in the Rupelian Ashley Formation by an antecedent ancestral taxon. As this tooth was found in situ in the Old Church, this explanation seems likely. In contrast, *Eosqualodon* is known only from the upper Oligocene (Chattian) Chandler Bridge Formation, and it also occurs in Europe where it is known only from the upper Oligocene (Chattian) and basal Miocene (Aquitainian). Therefore, the known stratigraphic range of *Eosqualodon* strongly suggests that the Pamunkey River *Eosqualodon* tooth did not come from the lower Oligocene (Rupelian) Old Church Formation. Instead, it seems likely that it came from a Chandler Bridge Formation interval that was erosionally removed by the Calvert sea when it transgressed across this region during the early Miocene.

About 50 miles (80 km) from the Old Church outcrops along the Pamunkey River (Figure 1), obliquely downdip to the southeast, the USGS-NASA Langley corehole (Edwards et al., 2005) recovered nearly 130 feet of Oligocene strata representing two units separated from one another by a distinct unconformity. The lower unit, which was called the "Drummonds Corner beds," is early Oligocene in age and about 25 feet thick; the upper unit, which was called the "Old Church Formation," is late Oligocene in age and about 105 feet thick. At the time of that report, the Old Church Formation generally was considered to be upper Oligocene in age, though soon after that its age was moved downward into the early Oligocene based on strontium-isotope dating (Weems et al., 2006). Therefore, the "Drummonds Corner beds" actually are the likely downdip equivalent of the Old Church Formation

and the “Old Church Formation” in this core hole is likely age-equivalent to the Chandler Bridge Formation, the Edisto Formation, or perhaps both.

The Oligocene strata in the USGS-NASA Langley corehole demonstrate that there was a relatively thick upper Oligocene unit once present in eastern Virginia that was largely removed by erosion prior to the deposition of the lower Miocene (Burdigalian) lower Calvert Popes Creek Sand Bed that today directly overlies the Old Church Formation above sea level in the Pamunkey River Valley region. Given the strongly phosphatized and worn appearance of the recovered *Eosqualodon* tooth (Fig. 3E), it seems quite reasonable to ascribe it to a specimen that originally was deposited in a late Oligocene “phantom unit” and subsequently reworked into the basal phosphate-rich lag deposit of the Popes Creek Sand Bed.

Based on their known stratigraphic range, the odontocete teeth here referred to *Ankyrorhiza* and *Xenorophus* likely came from the Old Church Formation, as could the tooth with affinity to *Cotylocara* and *Echovenator*. However, it is at least possible that some of this material also might be reworked from the late Oligocene phantom unit rather than from the early Oligocene Old Church Formation. Based on its degree of wear and phosphatization, it is plausible to argue that the tooth of *Ankyrorhiza* could be reworked. However, the much better preserved *Xenorophus* tooth is likely to be from the Old Church Formation, and the tooth with affinity to *Cotylocara* and *Echovenator* was certainly found within the Old Church Formation.

The six Oligocene cetacean taxa recognized here are represented by a total of only eleven specimens. The diversity of taxa within such a small sample suggests that the whale fauna from which they were derived probably included many more taxa than the six so far randomly discovered. This suggestion is supported by the

great diversity of whales now known from the nearly contemporaneous Givhans Ferry Member of the Ashley Formation in South Carolina, which includes two archaeomysticetes, two or three toothed mysticetes, four or five xenorophids, five or six agorophiid- and/or simocetid-grade odontocetes, and at least one waipatiid-grade odontocete. Before the massive expansion of Oligocene exposures in South Carolina that resulted from urbanization that began in the 1960's, the Ashley Formation was only known to have produced a few species of cetaceans. It is likely that the rarity of Old Church Formation exposures similarly has created a false impression that it has a seemingly depauperate fauna.

The most striking difference between the Old Church cetacean fauna and the much better sampled upper Ashley and Chandler Bridge formation faunas is that mysticete remains are relatively much more abundant in the Old Church Formation than they are in the Ashley or Chandler Bridge formations. In the Old Church Formation, odontocetes (seven specimens) so far occur about twice as often as mysticetes (four specimens) (a ratio of 2:1). In contrast, in the upper Ashley and Chandler Bridge formations the odontocete remains far outnumber the remains of mysticetes (likely 10:1, though a precise count has not been attempted). This difference could well be an artifact of spotty collecting in the Old Church Formation, but at face value it suggests that eastern American mysticetes in the Oligocene may have been far more common in the more northerly waters north of modern Cape Hatteras than they were in more southerly waters south of modern Cape Hatteras. Alternatively, collection bias towards larger mysticete remains in a challenging collecting environment also may explain this apparent difference. It is to be hoped that future collecting will allow us to determine if this difference in the relative abundance of odontocete and mysticete remains north and south of the Cape Hatteras region is real. More meaningful comparisons between the Virginia

Oligocene cetacean fauna and the South Carolina Oligocene cetacean faunas also will depend on whether further collecting can improve the presently sparse and fragmentary Old Church Formation record with better preserved and more complete remains.

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